

Title

A Six-Gene Transcriptomic Signature Linked to Extracellular Vesicle-Associated Features in Paediatric Severe Malarial Anaemia

Authors

Madhavi Sanjay Shukla^{1*}, Ashwin Warudkar^{2*}

¹ Indian Institute of Science Education and Research (IISER) Tirupati, India

² National Centre for Biological Sciences (NCBS) Bangalore, India

*Contributed equally

Corresponding authors

Madhavi Sanjay Shukla: shukla.madhavi13@gmail.com

Ashwin Warudkar: toconnectashwin@gmail.com

Abstract

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are increasingly recognised as involved in intracellular communication in systemic diseases, yet their precise function remains unclear. Severe malarial anaemia (SMA), a dangerous condition associated with infection by *Plasmodium falciparum*, is characterised by red blood cell lysis, inadequate red blood cell production, and abnormal immune regulation. Although host gene expression is known to be significantly altered in SMA, how these intracellular changes are linked to extracellular signalling mechanisms, particularly those involving EVs, remains unclear. This study uses an integrated systems biology approach, combining publicly available paediatric RNA sequencing data (GSE255403) with EV-related proteins from the ExoCarta database. Our analysis showed that EV-associated genes form an organised transcriptional module that plays roles in iron metabolism, immune responses, oxidative stress, metabolic functions, and host-parasite interactions, as determined through functional and network analyses. This module governs several key processes, including iron metabolism, immunological responses, oxidative stress response, general metabolic processes, and interactions between the parasite and the host. The current work identified a six-gene SMA-associated module (TFRC, CD274, BSG, PRDX2, SLC16A1, and HSPA1A) characterised by strong co-expression (Pearson correlation $r = 0.74$ – 0.95) and central integration within the protein–protein interaction network. The proposed model demonstrated high discriminatory power, as evidenced by ROC analysis (AUC = 0.909). In addition, cross-platform validation of this module was performed on another microarray dataset (GSE1124), which confirmed the relevance of this result. Overall, it suggests that EV-associated genes form a non-randomly concerted functional transcriptional module.

Keywords: Severe Malarial Anaemia (SMA), Extracellular Vesicles, Transcriptomics, *Plasmodium falciparum*, Host-Parasite Interaction, Gene Signature, Pathogenesis

Introduction

Globally, malaria accounts for hundreds of millions of infections annually, with the majority of deaths occurring in children under five years of age in Africa ((gmp), 2024). Severe malarial anaemia (SMA) is one of the most serious complications of *Plasmodium falciparum* infection. It continues to be a major cause of illness and death among children living in malaria-endemic regions (Perkins *et al*, 2011). SMA is characterised by a significant drop in haemoglobin levels, resulting from a combination of haemolysis, impaired erythropoiesis, and dysregulated immune responses. While the direct destruction of erythrocytes by the parasite is a key driver of SMA, there is growing evidence that host transcriptional responses also play an important role in determining disease severity and progression (Anyona *et al*, 2024). In addition to these processes, factors such as splenic sequestration of erythrocytes, bone marrow suppression, and altered iron metabolism further contribute to the severity of anaemia (White, 2018; Perkins *et al*, 2011; Casals-Pascual *et al*, 2006; Gwamaka *et al*, 2012).

High-throughput transcriptomic technologies have enabled examination of host functional responses to malaria infection at the molecular level. Large-scale RNA sequencing datasets, including GSE255403, have revealed extensive transcriptional reprogramming in paediatric SMA. For instance, more than 1000 genes have been reported to be differentially expressed between SMA and non-SMA cases, reflecting widespread perturbation of immune and metabolic networks (Anyona *et al*, 2024). These changes involve pathways related to innate immune signalling, erythropoiesis, cellular stress responses, and metabolism (Anyona *et al*, 2024). Such findings suggest that SMA cannot be explained by parasite burden alone, but rather reflects a complex interaction between host immune regulation and broader physiological responses. Studies of gene expression profiles and proteomics, have shown that some immune pathways, such as Toll-like receptor (TLR) activation and HSP (Heat shock protein) signalling, are disturbed in SMA (Onyango *et al*, 2024). These findings are further supported by recent microarray-based research that links gene expression patterns to clinical markers like lactatemia and haemoglobin levels and shows diverse transcriptional signatures across various malaria symptoms (Boldt *et al*, 2019). Together, these findings suggest that SMA involves coordinated host-response networks extending beyond isolated cellular events. However, although these studies reveal extensive intracellular transcriptional disruption, they provide limited insight into how these molecular signals may be coordinated and propagated across different cellular environments during systemic disease.

The ability of EVs to act as messengers by shuttling proteins, lipids, and RNAs between cells has gained increasing attention (Mantel & Marti, 2014; Regev-Rudzki *et al*, 2013). EV-mediated transfer of regulatory molecules has been implicated in immune modulation, inflammation, and pathogen communication in several infectious diseases (Mantel & Marti, 2014; Regev-Rudzki *et al*, 2013; Mantel *et al*, 2013). In the case of malaria, EVs produced by infected erythrocytes have been found to contain biologically active molecules that might influence host responses, parasite physiology, and, therefore, the progression of the disease (Kioko *et al*, 2023; Mantel & Marti, 2014). Thus, EVs may serve as a key intermediary linking intracellular transcriptional regulation with extracellular signalling networks.

Despite increasing insights into SMA transcriptomics and EV biology independently, studies integrating these two approaches remain limited. Specifically, it remains unclear whether transcriptionally altered gene expressions in SMA are preferentially associated with EV cargo or whether such overlap occurs by chance alone. Understanding this relationship may provide important insight into how intracellular transcriptional responses contribute to systemic disease pathology in SMA. In this study, we employed an integrative systems biology framework to investigate the intersection between intracellular transcriptomic alterations and EV-associated molecular signatures in paediatric SMA. Using publicly available RNA-seq data (GSE255403) (Anyona *et al*, 2024), we identified differentially expressed genes (DEGs) and compared them with EV cargo profiles from the ExoCarta database (Keerthikumar *et al*, 2016). Through functional enrichment, co-expression analysis, and protein–protein interaction modelling, we examined whether EV-associated genes form a coordinated transcriptional module linked to key regulatory pathways in SMA.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Data Sources

We identified and characterised pathogenesis-associated gene profiles connected to extracellular vesicles (EVs) in paediatric SMA using an integrative systems-level framework. We obtained gene expression profiles from the publicly available RNA-seq dataset GSE255403 (Anyona *et al*, 2024), including count data and corresponding sample metadata, and used them as input for downstream analysis. We used the count data and corresponding sample metadata as input for all subsequent downstream analyses. The EV protein information was obtained from the ExoCarta database (Keerthikumar *et al*, 2016), an extensive resource that compiles experimentally confirmed components of EVs. We combined these databases to study the congruence between changes in gene expression within cells and changes in EV molecules. The samples were classified into two categories based on their clinical conditions, namely, SMA and non-SMA.

We validated the discovered gene signatures using an independent microarray data set, GSE1124 (Boldt *et al*, 2019), comprising whole-blood gene expression from malaria patients and control samples. All analyses were done using R version 4.5.2.

Identification and Characterisation of EV-Associated Differentially Expressed Genes

We processed the RNA-seq count data using the DESeq2 package in R. During preprocessing, we removed duplicate gene entries and normalised gene identifiers. We matched the count matrix with the corresponding sample metadata. We then constructed a DESeq DataSet object using disease condition (SMA vs non-SMA) as the experimental design. Through the DESeq2 package, we modelled the count data using a negative binomial distribution and estimated dispersion, and \log_2 fold changes via shrinkage. The DEGs were determined by employing the following criteria: 1) Adjusted p-value (Benjamini-Hochberg) < 0.05 and 2) Absolute \log_2 fold change > 1 . We used the resulting gene list for all downstream analyses.

To investigate the relationship between host transcriptional alterations and extracellular vesicle (EV)-associated molecular signatures, we compared the DEGs with a curated list of EV-associated proteins obtained from the ExoCarta database (top 100 exosomal proteins). We identified overlapping genes by intersecting shared gene symbols between the two datasets. We visualised the overlap between SMA-associated DEGs and EV-related genes using Euler diagrams generated with the ‘eulerr’ package.

To further characterise the biological relevance of the identified genes, we performed Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis using the ‘clusterProfiler’ package. We converted gene symbols to Entrez IDs using the ‘org.Hs.eg.db’ package and focused on Biological Process (BP) GO terms. We identified significantly enriched pathways using a Benjamini–Hochberg-adjusted p-value threshold of < 0.05 and visualised the enriched terms using dot plots.

We next applied variance-stabilising transformation (VST) to the count data in DESeq2 to minimise variance associated with sequencing depth and improve downstream expression

analysis. Using the transformed expression matrix, we performed hierarchical clustering of EV-associated genes with Euclidean distance and complete linkage to evaluate similarities in expression patterns between SMA and non-SMA samples.

We computed 95% confidence intervals by extracting \log_2 fold changes and associated standard errors from the DESeq2 output. The amount and direction of differential expression were then visualised using effect-size plots.

Network and Functional Characterisation of EV-Associated Genes

To investigate potential functional relationships among EV-associated genes, we constructed a protein–protein interaction (PPI) network using interaction data from the STRING database (v12.0). We downloaded STRING interaction files and annotation datasets locally and mapped STRING protein identifiers to corresponding gene symbols using the annotation files. We retained interactions with a minimum confidence score of 0.4 to improve the biological relevance of the resulting network.

We developed the network interactions using the ‘igraph’ package and then transformed the network into the ‘tidygraph’ format for subsequent analysis and visualisation. Degree centrality was computed for each node in the network, and hubs were identified based on network connectivity properties. The EV-related genes were then mapped on the interaction network.

To examine the potential biological roles of EV-associated genes in SMA, we manually annotated genes according to previously reported associations with SMA-related biological processes, including iron homeostasis and erythropoiesis, immunomodulation, oxidative stress, metabolism, and host–parasite interactions. We assigned genes to one or more biological categories based on supporting evidence from the literature and incorporated direction of differential expression into the annotation framework.

We assessed co-expression patterns among EV-associated genes using Pearson’s correlation analysis on variance-stabilised expression values. We generated a correlation matrix and performed hierarchical clustering to identify genes with similar expression patterns. To find clusters of genes with comparable expression patterns, we used hierarchical clustering.

Classification Modelling and External Validation

We built a multivariate logistic regression model as a supervised classification approach, where we utilised the expression levels of six chosen genes: TFRC, CD274, BSG, PRDX2, SLC16A1, and HSPA1A to classify the EV-associated gene signature. Before modelling, we log-transformed gene expression values and used the “pROC” program to generate receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves from model-predicted probabilities. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) was used to evaluate the model’s performance.

We validated the identified gene signature using an independent microarray dataset (GSE1124). We processed the raw microarray data and mapped probe identifiers to gene symbols using the hgu133a annotation file. Based on the available sample annotations, we grouped samples into disease and control categories. We compared gene expression levels

between groups using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and visualised expression differences with boxplots.

Software and Computational Environment

All analyses were carried out using R (version 4.5.2). Important R packages used include:

- DESeq2 (differential gene expression)
- clusterProfiler (enrichment analysis)
- igraph, tidygraph, ggraph (network analysis)
- pheatmap (heat maps)
- pROC (ROC curves)
- ggplot2 and related packages (visualisation)

The complete annotated R script and associated data are provided in Supplementary File S1.

RESULTS

Differential Gene Expression in SMA

We performed host transcriptomic profiling using publicly available RNA-seq data on host genes involved in SMA development. The raw counts, along with their respective metadata, have been processed with DESeq2 for differential expression analysis.

DEGs, with a significant difference in their expression levels between SMA and non-SMA groups, were selected based on an adjusted p-value of less than 0.05 and an absolute log₂ fold change >1. These genes were considered as DEGs. This information has been presented in brackets below, along with the supplementary file containing the list of DEGs (DEG_results.csv).

Further analysis of the genes involved in the extracellular component of SMA was done by intersecting the DEG list with an EV protein database from ExoCarta. From the visualisation of the differential expression landscape (Figure 1A), a distinct segregation of upregulated and downregulated DEGs is observed. Of the six DEGs associated with EVs, four showed significant upregulation and two significant downregulation in SMA patients, suggesting that EV-associated transcripts are represented in both induced and suppressed transcriptional programs in SMA.

To examine more comprehensively the biological importance of these changes in transcription, we conducted a Gene Ontology analysis on the significantly changed genes (DEGs) (Figure 1B). The biological functions that were found to be enriched included erythrocyte differentiation, heme biosynthesis, myeloid cell homeostasis, and metabolic processes, suggesting that the affected pathways include erythropoiesis and immune regulation in SMA. Together, these findings define the broader transcriptional landscape of SMA and establish the basis for subsequent integration with EV-associated molecular signatures.

Integration of EV-associated transcripts reveals coordinated molecular networks in SMA.

To test whether transcriptional changes in SMA include components of extracellular signalling pathways, we undertook an integrated analysis in which host-origin DEGs were overlapped with the extracellular vesicle (EV) cargo. This led to the identification of a subgroup of overlapping genes encoding transcripts that are both differentially expressed and likely transported by EVs (Figure 2A).

To examine the properties of the EV-associated genes, we investigated their expression levels across all samples using variance-stabilised counts. Clustering analysis without labels was performed to determine whether there is separation between samples belonging to SMA and those that do not. Indeed, genes are separated into two clusters, indicating that they preserve disease-specific expression patterns (Figure 2B).

To understand the nature of differential expression of these genes, we examined the range of changes using log₂ fold change and confidence interval plots. These results showed that EV-associated genes are indeed differentially expressed, but this difference is heterogeneous, including both up- and down-regulated components (Figure 2C).

To explore whether these genes are interrelatedly regulated, we constructed a network of interactions between EV-associated genes and the proteins they interact with. As seen from our results, EV-associated genes interact within an interactive landscape and do not exist independently (Figure 2D). Hubs such as EGFR, RHOA, and CTNNB1 were identified as the main regulatory hubs using network analysis. At the same time, EV-associated genes were found in nodes where different molecules interacted.

Functional Coordination and Co-expression of EV-associated Genes

To further explore the biologically relevant functions of the EV-gene cluster, we analysed the relationships between their biological functions and coexpression within the SMA transcriptomic profile. Functional mapping of the six EV-gene targets in relation to their involvement in specific SMA-related biological pathways indicated that each of the selected EV-genes played a role in at least one biological pathway involved in SMA disease, with all of the selected genes together covering multiple aspects of SMA pathology, such as iron regulation, immune modulation, oxidative stress, parasite interaction, and metabolic stress (Figure 3A). Each gene was mapped individually to the pathway in which it was involved: TFRC for iron homeostasis, CD274 for immune modulation, PRDX2 for oxidative stress, and SLC16A1 for metabolic stress.

To test whether these genes function synchronously, we assessed their expression relationships using pairwise correlation analysis. The results of the Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong positive associations ($r = 0.74-0.95$), indicating a highly synchronised transcriptional program. (Figure 3B). Using hierarchical clustering analysis, we identified gene clusters with identical expression behaviours.

Collectively, these findings indicate that EV-associated genes form a coordinated transcriptional module linked to multiple biological processes relevant to SMA pathology.

Diagnostic Performance and External Validation of EV-associated Gene Signature

To evaluate whether the EV-associated signature could be reproduced across independent datasets and experimental platforms, we validated the findings using the GSE1124 microarray dataset.

We sought to assess the classification performance of the EV-related gene panel using multivariate logistic regression to differentiate SMA from non-SMA samples. The ROC curves showed substantial discriminatory power of the six-gene signature, with an AUC of 0.909 (Figure 4A).

To test the generalizability of the gene signature associated with EVs, we used another independent dataset (GSE1124). The dataset consists of transcriptomic profiling data from whole blood samples of patients and healthy individuals with malaria. Despite differences in disease background and platforms, several genes in the signature showed concordant expression patterns across the two samples (Figure 4B). In particular, there was a statistical difference in the expression levels of BSG, TFRC, and HSPA1A, whereas for PRDX2 and SLC16A1, only similar tendencies were observed without statistical differences.

Together, these findings suggest that the genes related to EVs exhibit a transcriptional signature that is not restricted to only the SMA dataset. Despite several differences between validation and discovery datasets, the transcriptional signature is conserved and consistent across datasets.

DISCUSSION

Severe malarial anaemia (SMA) is a complex manifestation of *Plasmodium falciparum* infection characterised by extensive haemoglobin depletion resulting from haemolysis, ineffective erythropoiesis, and dysregulated immune responses (White, 2018; Casals-Pascual *et al*, 2006; Perkins *et al*, 2011). In the present study, we identified an EV-associated transcriptional program linked to paediatric SMA using an integrative systems-level framework combining host transcriptomic profiling with extracellular vesicle (EV) signatures. Our findings indicate that EV-associated genes in SMA do not represent isolated transcriptional events but instead form a coordinated molecular module associated with iron homeostasis, immune regulation, oxidative stress, metabolism, and host–parasite interactions.

Our analysis of the available transcriptomic data showed that many pathways linked to erythropoiesis, haem biosynthesis, and metabolism were dysregulated in SMA (Anyona *et al*, 2024). Many genes linked to erythropoiesis and haem-related pathways showed altered transcription despite the persistence of severe anaemia, suggesting that transcriptional activation alone may not translate into effective erythropoiesis in SMA (Anyona *et al*, 2024; Casals-Pascual *et al*, 2006). This observation is consistent with previous studies describing dyserythropoiesis and impaired bone marrow responses in SMA patients (Perkins *et al*, 2011; Casals-Pascual *et al*, 2006). Together, these findings further support the concept that SMA pathogenesis extends beyond direct parasite-mediated erythrocyte destruction and involves broader dysregulation of the host response.

In addition to erythropoietic anomalies, our study also provides evidence of immune dysregulation in SMA. Earlier research has highlighted the role of cytokine signal transduction pathways and immune checkpoint functions in malaria pathogenesis (Lyke *et al*, 2004; Wykes *et al*, 2014; Ribas & Wolchok, 2018). From this perspective, the involvement of CD274 (PD-L1) in the described EV gene network supports the activation of immunological control pathways that could lead to immune clearance failure. Such evidence corroborates previous observations on T-cell exhaustion and abnormal cytokine levels in SMA cases (Wykes *et al*, 2014; Lyke *et al*, 2004). Not only do our results highlight intracellular transcriptional changes, but they also suggest that some dysregulated genes in SMA could mediate intercellular communication via EVs

The convergence between differentially expressed genes of hosts and EV-associated cargo is particularly relevant because EVs released from *Plasmodium falciparum*-infected erythrocytes have previously been implicated in intercellular communication, immune modulation, and host–parasite signalling (Regev-Rudzki *et al*, 2013; Mantel *et al*, 2013; Kioko *et al*, 2023). In addition, emerging evidence suggests that parasite-derived EV cargo may participate in post-transcriptional regulation and systemic immune responses during infection (Kioko *et al*, 2023; Mantel *et al*, 2013). Together with other studies, our observations suggest that EV-associated transcriptional programs contribute to the systemic coordination of host responses observed in SMA.

The six genes identified in the EV-associated signature are interconnected and involved in SMA pathology. TFRC reflects disruption of iron homeostasis, which has been strongly associated with severe malaria progression and anaemia severity (Gwamaka *et al*, 2012; Lelliott *et al*, 2015; White, 2018). BSG functions as a key receptor involved in *P. falciparum* erythrocyte invasion (Crosnier *et al*, 2011). In addition, PRDX2 and HSPA1A are linked to oxidative stress responses and cellular protective mechanisms that become critical during parasite-induced oxidative injury (Becker *et al*, 2004; Lelliott *et al*, 2015).

Rather than functioning independently, these genes appear to represent multiple interconnected aspects of the host response to severe infection. Furthermore, the coordinated expression and regulation observed in EV-associated genes provide additional evidence for their role in a regulated transcriptional module rather than as isolated transcriptional events. Co-expression studies revealed a significant positive correlation among several genes in the signature. On the other hand, protein-protein interaction analyses placed EV-associated genes within a network of highly interconnected regulatory systems, with genes such as EGFR, RHOA, and CTNNB1 serving as hubs. This indicates that EV-induced transcriptional signatures might be involved in host transcriptional processes associated with immune signalling, stress response, and adaptation in SMA (Anyona *et al*, 2024; Mantel *et al*, 2013).

The identified EV-associated transcriptional signature, originally based on RNA-seq data, was validated for reproducibility using the independent GSE1124 microarray dataset. Notably, several core genes in this signature (BSG, TFRC, HSPA1A, and SLC16A1) showed consistent, statistically significant expression patterns across both platforms. This cross-platform reproducibility confirms the biological relevance of the identified transcriptional module.

Our findings are further supported by previous transcriptomic and multi-omics studies investigating severe malaria pathogenesis (Anyona *et al*, 2024; Boldt *et al*, 2019). Earlier RNA-seq and proteomic studies have identified dysregulation of immune signalling pathways, oxidative stress responses, HSP-related pathways, and metabolic alterations in SMA (Anyona *et al*, 2024; Boldt *et al*, 2019; Becker *et al*, 2004). In particular, disturbances involving HSP70-TLR signalling and glutamine metabolism have been implicated in severe disease progression (Onyango *et al*, 2024; Kempaiah *et al*, 2016). The inclusion of HSPA1A within the EV-associated transcriptional module identified in our study supports previous observations linking stress-response pathways with malaria-associated immunopathology.

Our study also has several limitations. First, the use of bulk RNA-seq data limits the ability to resolve transcriptional changes at the cell-type level, which may be particularly relevant in the context of complex host responses in severe malarial anaemia. Second, the association between the identified genes and extracellular vesicle (EV) biology was inferred from an integrative bioinformatics analysis of curated EV datasets and does not directly demonstrate a vesicular origin, secretion, or functional involvement. Therefore, the EV-related interpretation of the identified gene signature should be considered hypothesis-generating and requires further validation in purified vesicle populations and experimental systems.

Finally, although the identified genes exhibit coordinated expression patterns, network connectivity, and consistent behaviour across independent datasets, functional validation studies are required to determine whether these genes actively contribute to EV-mediated signalling processes or reflect downstream consequences of systemic disease. Despite these limitations, the integrative framework and cross-platform consistency support the biological relevance of the identified transcriptional module and provide a foundation for future experimental investigation.

In conclusion, overall, the current study reports the discovery of a transcriptional network associated with EVs that corresponds to important biological functions relevant to SMA. Combining host transcriptomic changes with those associated with EVs is a holistic approach that helps understand the link between intracellular changes and extracellular signalling events in the context of severe malaria infection. Although additional experiments are needed for confirmation, our results suggest that transcriptional profiles associated with EVs may serve as potential biomarkers of SMA.

Data Availability

The RNA-seq dataset analysed in this study is publicly available from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) under accession number GSE255403. The independent validation dataset GSE1124 is also available from GEO. Extracellular vesicle-associated genes were obtained from the ExoCarta database, and protein–protein interaction data were derived from the STRING database (v12.0). All processed data, along with the complete annotated R scripts used for analysis, are provided in **Supplementary File S1**.

Acknowledgements

We thank RV, NK, AJ, NG, GR, and KLV for their valuable feedback and constructive discussions.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Author Contributions

M.S.S.: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Visualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

A.W.: Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1A Differential Gene Expression Profile: Volcano plot showing differential gene expression between SMA and non-SMA samples. Each dot corresponds to a gene, which is plotted using \log_2 fold change along the x-axis and negative \log_{10} of adjusted p-value along the y-axis. Significantly differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (adjusted p-value < 0.05 , $\log_2FC > 1$) are marked in the graph with different colours: red for upregulated genes and blue for downregulated genes. Those genes involved in extracellular vesicles (EVs), selected by intersecting with the ExoCarta database, are highlighted in black. Selected highly significant genes are annotated based on their statistical significance, including CD274 and BSG. **Figure 1B Functional Enrichment Analysis:** Gene Ontology (GO) functional enrichment analysis of differential expression (DEGs) of SMA. Enriched biological process (BP) GO terms were identified using clusterProfiler overrepresentation analysis. Each point indicates an enriched function in which the gene ratio indicates the size, while the colour represents the adjusted p-value. Functional enrichment analysis highlighted pathways associated with erythropoiesis, haem biosynthesis, myeloid cell differentiation, and metabolic regulation. Significance of enriched terms was computed by adjusted p-value (Benjamini-Hochberg correction, adjusted $p < 0.05$).

Figure 2A Convergence of SMA Transcriptome and EV Cargo: Euler diagram showing the overlap between DEGs detected in SMA (i.e., the GSE255403 dataset) and proteins associated with extracellular vesicles (EVs) extracted from the ExoCarta database. The overlap identifies a subset of transcriptionally dysregulated genes associated with EV cargo. **Figure 2B Expression Profile of EV-Associated Convergent Genes:** Heatmap representing the differential expression pattern of EV-associated genes in SMA and non-SMA samples using variance-stabilised transformed expression values. Genes are represented on rows, while samples are represented on columns. Hierarchical clustering was performed for both genes and samples. Distinct clustering between SMA and non-SMA samples indicates disease-associated expression patterns among EV-associated genes. **Figure 2C Differential Expression Magnitude of EV-associated Genes:** Forest plot showing \log_2 fold changes with corresponding 95% confidence intervals of EV-associated differentially expressed genes. Points represent \log_2 fold change estimates, whereas the horizontal bars denote the confidence intervals computed by DESeq2. Statistical significance was derived from DESeq2 adjusted p-values ($p_{adj} < 0.05$). Red and blue points indicate upregulated and downregulated genes, respectively. **Figure 2D EV-Associated Genes Integrate into Central Regulatory Network in SMA:** A PPI network was built from the interactions in the STRING database. Nodes correspond to proteins, and edges denote established or predicted biological connections. Gold

nodes denote EV-related genes, whereas red nodes represent high-centrality hub genes identified through degree centrality analysis. The network indicates that the genes associated with EVs lie at the centre of the interaction network and interact with the regulatory hub proteins, such as EGFR, RHOA, and CTNNB1.

Figure 3A Functional Mapping of EV-associated Genes in SMA: Tile plot showing the relationships between EV-associated genes and SMA-relevant biological processes. Rows correspond to individual genes and columns to biological processes such as iron dysregulation, immune suppression, oxidative stress, parasite interactions, and metabolic stress. Green tiles indicate reported associations between genes and biological processes, whereas grey tiles indicate no reported association. Coloured dots indicate the direction of differential expression, with red indicating up-regulation and blue indicating down-regulation. **Figure 3B Co-expression Patterns of EV-associated Genes:** Heatmap showing pairwise Pearson correlation coefficients among EV-associated genes using variance-stabilised expression values. Colour intensity represents the strength and direction of correlation, with colours ranging from negative (blue) to positive (red). The values in the cells correspond to the respective Pearson correlation coefficients. Hierarchical clustering was applied to both rows and columns. Strong positive correlations among multiple genes indicate coordinated expression patterns within the EV-associated gene set.

Figure 4A: Classification Performance of EV-Associated Gene Signature: Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve showing the classification performance of the six-gene EV-associated signature (TFRC, CD274, BSG, PRDX2, SLC16A1, HSPA1A) between SMA and non-SMA samples using a multivariate logistic regression model. The plot illustrates the relationship between true positive rate (sensitivity) and false-positive rate (1-specificity). The diagonal reference line represents classification performance expected by chance. The six-gene signature demonstrated strong discriminatory performance with an AUC of 0.909. Performance was determined from the ROC AUC without hypothesis testing. **Figure 4B External Validation of EV-Associated Gene Signature:** Boxplots showing the expression patterns of EV-associated genes (BSG, HSPA1A, PRDX2, SLC16A1, TFRC) in control and malaria groups from the independent dataset GSE1124. Expression values were derived from microarray-based whole-blood transcriptomic profiles. Differences in statistical significance between the groups were analysed using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test, and p-values are denoted on each graph (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ns: not significant). The expression levels of BSG, TFRC, and HSPA1A significantly differed between groups, whereas PRDX2 and SLC16A1 showed no significant differences.